

CULTURALLY ORIENTED ELT TEXTBOOKS AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

¹Muhammad Umer Azim, ²Azhar Munir Bhatti, ³Zaheer Hussain, ⁴Muhammad Iqbal

ABSTRACT

The perceptions of English language teachers about cultural orientation in ELT materials were the basic motive behind writing this article. Teaching of English has travelled a lot like from teaching of it as a foreign language to another phase of teaching it as second language and now it has adopted the role of an international language. These paradigm shifts demand specific kind of teaching of specific materials. Spread of English as an important element of globalization and birth of world Englishes demand different cultural treatment in ELT materials. Current study investigated teachers' perceptions on the inclusion of the culture of native speakers, local culture and culture at international level in ELT materials. A questionnaire is used to collect data which has both quantitative and qualitative elements. It was analysed using simple statistical tool and coding. The results showed positive attitude of the teachers regarding inclusion of diverse cultures in ELT materials.

Key words: ELT Materials, EIL, Cultural orientation, Globalization, world Englishes

1. Introduction

The article focuses on the perceptions of language teachers (LT) on the cultural orientation of English Language Teaching (ELT) textbooks. Current issues like globalization and local identity, migration and immigrants' identity, intolerance for different cultures resulting in wars and terrorist activities, increased hatred etc. have given rise to the metanarrative that educational institutions fail to deliver their desired outcomes. The desired outcomes are to produce learned-learners, who are more tolerant, more appreciative of cultural diversity, and more humane etc. This leads to rethinking of our national goals, curricular aims and syllabus objectives. In this globalized world, the importance of international communication has increased enormously. This communication is effectively possible if common code i.e. lingua franca of the age is promoted, developed and taught efficiently and carefully. This makes English, at present, very important as it has attained the status of international language. Teaching of English language is subject of research for more than a century now.

¹University of Management & Technology Lahore Pakistan

³National University of Modern Languages Lahore Campus

²Higher Education Department, Punjab, Pakistan

⁴University of Management of Technology Lahore, Pakistan

The domains like; language learning theories, language teaching methods, syllabus design, teaching of basic language skills, error analysis, evaluation of textbooks, etc. have been explored and will be explored as constructs are in constant flux. Current study focuses on the cultural elements in ELT textbooks as perceived by the language teachers. It focused on the following questions:

- a. Is it important to include culture in ELT textbooks?
- b. Is it important to include culture of native speakers of target language?
- c. Is it important to include the learner's culture?
- d. Is it important to include other non-native cultures?
- e. What percentage of the content should focus culture of; native speakers and non-native speakers?

This study is mixed method because of having quantitative and qualitative elements as the tool of collecting data is questionnaire. Questionnaire is designed for fixed responses along with open ended request to give reasons for their particular choices.

The article will give brief introduction of the status of English language at present. It will be followed by a sketchy review of historic developments of methods and approaches in English language teaching to understand various trends in the inclusions of cultures while teaching language. Then the focus of discussion will be on using ELT textbook and those textbook features that can make a textbook better than the others.

2. Background

Today English has taken the charge of a lingua franca to cater the needs of communication in the world. It is used for communication in number of countries. Its use both as native and foreign or second language is widespread. It is present in the academic institutions of almost every country. It is being taught as a subject in some country and in some other countries it is treated as EMI (English as a medium of Instruction). It is a living and vibrant language of present times. English is spoken and understood in different countries of the world which includes the United States of America (USA), Ireland, the British Isles, Australia, Canada, New Zealand, Liberia, the Republic of South Africa, and many colonies/ countries under the United Kingdom and the USA. According to an estimate English is most widely spoken second language of the world as there are 300 million people who are using it as L2 and there are more 100 million fluent speakers who speak English as an FL. Besides that, around one billion people living in the world who have knowledge of English. They can be categorized into native speakers and English users to take it as L2 or FL. History briefs us that bilingualism or multilingualism is no more an exception rather it has become a norm. Now the figures reflect that almost 60% of the population has become multilingual today. It implicates that language teaching and learning is and will be an important factor of development. The proven fact is that the languages take places of prominence as now English is in fame but some centuries ago this place was with Roman and still some more centuries ago it was for Greek. In the sixteenth century, socio-political developments in Europe give importance to their local languages like Italian, French, German, etc.

The growing importance of English language made it necessary for the institutions of the world to teach it to produce appropriate product for the market. The methods and approaches we are using today developed through history. The history of language teaching especially English language teaching is briefly reviewed here.

With the lessening of importance for Latin, its study took a very different and interesting role. The study of classical Latin provided the first model of foreign language teaching with analysis of its grammar and rhetoric. So, we can trace back the history of language teaching to the comparative teaching of classical Latin at ‘grammar schools’ of England. Grammar of Latin was taught through memorization of grammatical rules, parsing, conjugations and declensions. For the purpose of translation or for producing writing samples, the use of parallel text in other languages was in vogue (Kelly, 1969; Howatt, 1984). Thus, in this approach literature of the native language is the key resource. This approach made the literary culture of the language the only aim of language teaching. It implicitly suggests the supremacy of language too over the learners’ language.

It was followed by ‘The Reform Movement’. It was developed in 1880s and the reformers believed in the following simple aspects.

1. The primary importance was given to speech
2. Inclusion of the findings of phonetics in teaching language
3. Listening should precede reading
4. Words should be taught in meaningful sentences
5. Inductive way of teaching should be used to teach Grammar
6. No translation should be used

The syllabuses which resulted from the Reform Movement emphasized careful selection and grading of materials to be taught. In this manner, they stood in sharp contrast with the parallel development in ELT. These developments were mentioned by Howatt (1984) as ‘natural methods of language teaching’. They were mentioned with the different names like; Natural Method, the Conversation Method etc. These methods ultimately led to the development of what became popular as the Direct Method. The methodology of this method was loosely structured as against the structured methodology proposed by the Reform Movement. The base of this new method was the theory that considers human language learning as a natural process. This natural process can be facilitated through proper conditions needed. To the method these conditions are ‘teachers as models’, ‘everyday topics of interest’, and ‘motivation to be understood’. This collection of methods emphasizes learning of native culture more. The topics related to native speakers’ life, economy, political ideologies and even geography of native speakers’ land are used to produce language teaching materials.

The twentieth century began with the explanation and classification of English language. In this regard the works of Gatenby, Hornby, and Wakefield (Advanced Learner Dictionary of Current English in 1953), Palmer and Blandford in 1939 (A Grammar of Spoken English on a Strictly Phonetic Basis), and Hornby in 1954 (Hornby’s Guide to Pattern and Usage in English) were very influential. These specialists developed Oral Approach or Situational Language Teaching. These books were developed based on systematic selection, grading and presentation of the language items. Situational language teaching along with the oral practice feature, grammar, and patterns of sentences impressed many classroom teachers practically so it continued to be used in the 1980s. This approach also promoted the topics in the previous approaches.

During the world wars and especially with the start of World War II language teaching entered a new phase. First method which appeared on the scene had the strong philosophical and theoretical basis. Its theory of language was based on structural linguistics and learning theory was on behavioral psychology. For psychologist like Skinner (1957) and Brown (1980) language learning was habit formation. The main focus of the method was to develop accuracy and fluency in the

oral skills. All other language skills: listening, reading comprehension, grammar, writing, and vocabulary were a tool to further enhance, enrich and polish the oral skills. Dialogues and drills constitute the major part of the classroom activities. Repetition and memorization were main skills learner should possess. It was most wide spread in 1960s. It was used in popular courses like English 900 and Lado English Series. The popularity of this method rapidly decreased because of the severe criticism on its theories of language and language learning. Chomsky (1966:153) declared “Language is not a habit structure. Ordinary linguistic behavior characteristically involves innovation, formation of new sentences and patterns in accordance with the rules of great abstractness and intricacy”. This approach was also called military approach and focused native like accent and pronunciation with deep knowledge of culture of target language. Here teaching of culture was explicit and thus ELT materials just focused culture of native speakers.

The criticism on structural methods by Chomsky in his acknowledged book ‘Syntactic Structures’ brought out some of the basic but important features of language, the uniqueness and creativity. British applied linguists point out some other fundamental characteristics of language – functional and communicative. The prominent scholars involved in providing the theoretical basis for communicative language teaching were Henry Widdowson, Christopher Candlin, John Firth, MAK Halliday, Dell Hymes, John Gumperz, William Labov, John Austin, John Searle. The method focused on developing ‘communicative competence’ (Hymes, 1972). It referred to the language knowledge and its ability for effective communication. The method emphasized real life communications tasks. It was a learner centered method and promoted teaching integrated skills. Communicative Language Teaching was best because of its flexibility features. It was and still is practiced all over the world with differences that have resulted from the individual’s interpretation of this method. It had the issues as pointed by Swan (1985) of teacher training, material development, testing and evaluation. But it was and still is very popular movement in language teaching world. Here we see a shift or development of this method. It started with ‘communicative competence’ which included ‘socio-linguistic’ competence. Socio-linguistics competence was elaborated as understanding of native speakers’ cultural values, norms and taboos. But this is changing rapidly as the communicative needs are changing for the English language learners.

Smith (1978) explains English as foreign language as a learning subject at school not as an independent language of communication. The purpose of teaching English was to enjoy English literature, movies, radio or television programs, limited use in restricted tourism and business. Native cultural study was a big component because the purpose was restricted to limited use of language with native speakers only. Stern (1992) explains foreign language learning as educational tool rather than immediate communicative application. Similarly, Nunan (1999) elaborates the EFL context where English is neither a tool of communication nor a medium of instruction.

The second phase of English language teaching started with British and American colonization. This phase is of teaching English as a second language. Here English takes the role of medium of instruction and lingua franca for the speakers of diverse regional languages. The examples are Philippines, Pakistan, India, Srilanka, etc. Lightbown and Spada (1993) support the same idea. There are number of researchers who are not satisfied with these terms because of their inability to explain current English language teaching situation like: Shaw (1981); Smith (1981); Campbell et al. (1982); Alptekin & Alptekin (1984); and Jenkins (1998). This was the advent of the third phase of English language teaching where new terms are searched for which can truly represent the state of English language all over the world.

This new term with which researchers tried to represent the current emerging situation of English language teaching is EIL, Smith (1976); Quirk (1978); Strevens (1978); Kachru & Quirk (1981); Smith (1981); Campbell et al. (1982); Stern (1992); Alptekin & Alptekin (1984); and Talebinezhad & Aliakbari (2001). Related terms are EIL (English as an International Language), EIAL (English as International Auxiliary Language), EWL (English as World Language) and EIIL (English as International or Intranational language) which have gained importance.

In the last two decades because of the rapid development in communication and transportation the phenomenon of globalization has emerged as a defining feature in many domains of life. It had enhanced the importance and demand of English Language by the world (Cogo & Dewey, 2012). This modern trend contributed to the fast internationalization process of English language. Language change through contact of different languages is a permanent feature of any language but in this globalized world English is coming in contact with diverse set of languages. Sharifian (2009, p. 2), defines EIL as a shift in the paradigm for SLA, TESOL, and the applied linguistics. It is because of the complexities attached with the “tremendously rapid spread of English” in recent decades. EIL demands critical evaluation of existing approaches, methodologies, notions, tools in the field of applied linguistics and sociolinguistics (Bolton, 2004; Kachru, 1986, 1992, p. 2)

Kachru’s (1986, 1992) three concentric circle model is important to explain the role of English around the world. It constitutes Inner Circle, the Outer Circle, and the Expanding Circle. First Circle that is inner represents countries where English is native language like; UK, USA, Canada, Australia, etc. The second circle i.e. outer is about those countries where English is considered L2 like Pakistan, India, Singapore, etc. Lastly, the last circle known as expanding includes Saudi Arabia, Iran, China, South Korea, etc. where English, at the moment, is treated as FL. Majority of learners and users of English belong to outer and expanding circles.

Matsuda (2003), links EIL’s recognition of World Englishes to ELT because of English speakers from different backgrounds. As Canagarajah (2006) argues that there is so much of interplay of outer and expanding circles’ Englishes with inner circle’s English that these circles are no more relevant (2006, p. 233). He says that as many varieties and the communities of English language are faced by the learner, the language proficiency will be complex and the learner has to increase his ability to communicate to deal with the varieties of the language. Here communicative competence’s component of socio-linguistic needs to be redefined.

Many prominent researchers have explored culture with relation to English language learning and teaching. Byram (1988, p. 82) defines culture as “shared and negotiated (knowledge) between people.” Adaskou, Britten, and Fahsi (1990) distinguish four separate sorts of “culture”: the esthetic, sociological, semantic, and pragmatic sense. Esthetic sense refers to literature, music, media, and cinema. Sociological sense involves customs and institutions of family and community life. Semantic sense refers meaning making in language. Pragmatic aspect includes understanding of history, social skills and extra-linguistic features. According to Baker (2015, p. 132), the qualities of intercultural competence are:

- (1) ability to practice communication in varied settings of a socio-culture;
- (2) ability to use the language proficiency with appropriateness and flexibility; and
- (3) communicative attitudes which include the skill to de-center and revitalize one’s own expectations, beliefs, and values.

Culture is emerging as an important issue in the discussions done previously. But more important is that EIL is more established in this globalized world. So, the teaching and learning

become a necessity rather than a luxury. Explicit teaching of English is done at all levels in almost every part of the world. That is why we discussed briefly at the start of the article the development of different teaching methods. This rich domain of approaches and methods of language teaching is self-suggestive of the importance of teaching-learning process.

Graves considers textbook a standard source to get information for a formal study and also an instrument to help teachers and learners both (2000). It is one of the important resources teacher can use to teach planned syllabus in an effective manner. It provides guidelines, framework and confidence to the teacher and learners. It also gives sense of unique achievement and teachers and learners progress in using textbook. It reduces the burden of the teacher and saves time and energy which will be spent on adapting and developing activities and materials. It also provides standardization because books are designed on the pre-decided set of skills and knowledge component and when all teachers use the same book then standardized learning can be assured. There are huge numbers of benefits of the books so need to be chosen carefully.

Text book evaluation is a subject of many prominent research scholars (Cunningsworth, 1995; Breen and Candlin 1987; Sheldon, 1988; Brown, 1994; McDonough and Shaw, 1993; Skierso, 1991). They gave detailed criteria for measuring the effectiveness of textbooks in a particular context. They touched upon every aspect of the book.

The researcher wants to discuss relatively a recent phenomenon of including culture in ELT books. Bartram (2010) indicates textbooks as one of the three major influences that effect learner's motivation. The inclusion of culture in ELT textbooks has always been a heated debate. One group promotes the culture and values of target language community. While the other group favours the inclusion of learner's culture. But EIL takes a step forward and there the needs and purposes of including cultures change.

An important element of EIL textbooks development is learners' experience of different varieties of English, and developing conscious of different cultures. McKay and BokhorstHeng (2008, p. 2) explains globalization as a "reformulation of social space in which the global and local are constantly interacting with one another." Here "globalization" is needed. It means the real flavor of EIL is to mix up the target and local cultures with multiple non-native cultures.

EIL suggests that English is frequently used for communication at cross-cultural level. This demands that materials in ELT books should be culturally sensitive and encourage learner to know about the variety of cultures. Learners can reflect on their cultural values to strengthen their identity. Here the primary purpose is not to learn about target language's culture but to sensitize learners to the variety of cultures so that they can communicate with them effectively. It will also solve the problem of terrorism and easy assimilation of culture. Learner will develop more respect towards divergent cultures. McKay (2002) proposes distinct attention to the culture in designing curriculum for teaching of EIL. She proposed inter-culturalism that includes cultural content from native countries, content from learners' culture and content from international culture, non-native countries. Byram, Gribkova and Starkey (2002, p. 22) define "inter-culturalism" to teach culture which aims to foster learners as intercultural mediators or speakers capable of understanding and appreciating language users as individuals with varied identities and avoid the stereo types related to a person, a group, a nation of some ethnic origins.

McKay (2012, p. 42) suggests some basic rules for teaching in EIL scenario:

- Multi-lingualism and multi-culturalism should be promoted;
- The policies and the planning regarding language should be localized;

- The learners should be made aware of the variations and use of an English language in contexts;
- Opportunity of learning English should be for everyone; and
- The concept of qualified English teachers should be refurbished.

Language and communication styles are loaded with cultural values and knowledge of these cultural values can produce accomplished users of language. There should be shared rules and regulation of not only language but communication strategies and this can only be done if we produce either curriculum or ELT materials with a variety of cultures. Well-designed teaching materials should be considered which should include abundance of linguistic samples of world Englishes with an emphasis on culture. Brown (2012, pp. 155–156) suggests that EIL curriculum developers should; provide strategies for handling cultural differences, include of global and local culture so that learners can communicate in both situations effectively, develop ownership and respect of local variety of English, include activities based on situations involving NS-NNS and NNS-NNS interactions.

Matsuda (2012, pp. 176–177) emphasizes the multiplicity of sources for gathering teaching material. The first resource can be the topics like world peace and environment conservation this will also help to make learners global citizens. The second source can be other NNS' culture(s) from different parts of the world. The third source can be learner's own culture for EIL teaching material.

All the discussion above emphasized that because English has now attained the status of international language then its teaching should be done accordingly and in this teaching the role of books or English language teaching materials is very important. Books should include cultural elements that can prepare learners for the future use of English language both with native speakers and non-native speakers. Again the perceptions of teachers are very important because the theory can only be confirmed through the implementation and experimentation which only teachers can do. So the study in hand is about the perceptions of English language teachers regarding cultural orientation in English language teaching textbooks.

3. Methodology

The study is about the perceptions of English language teachers regarding cultural orientation in English language teaching textbooks. The element of culture is becoming extremely important in the context of globalization, language and identity, language and culture, world Englishes, and English as an international language. At present English is taught as an international language and this aspect demands a different cultural orientation in ELT materials. The study investigated the perceptions of English language teachers regarding this important issue.

3.1. Research Design

The study is mixed method approach. It has qualitative as well as quantitative elements.

3.2. Instrument of Data Collection

A questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents/participants. Questionnaire was consisted of close ended quantitative questions and respondents were asked to give qualitative reasons for their choices. (See appendix A)

3.3. Population

The population was consisted of English language teachers of Lahore at undergraduate level. Thirty teachers were randomly selected and their data is given in table 3.1.

Table 3.1

General Profile of participants

General Information		Numbers
Gender:	Male	17
	Female	13
Education:	MA	10
	M. Phil	17
	PhD	03
Age:	21-30	10
	31-40	16
	41-50	04
Experience	0-5	9
	5-10	18
	10+	03

3.4. Research Questions

1. Is it important to include culture in ELT textbooks?
2. Is it important to include culture of native speakers of target language?
3. Is it important to include the learner's culture?
4. Is it important to include other non-native cultures?
5. What percentage of the content should focus culture of; native speakers and non-native speakers?

3.5. Data Analysis

Data was analysed using simple percentages. The qualitative data was studied for emerging themes and codes were provided. The comments were mentioned with the analysis of questions.

4. Data Analysis & Discussion

1. In response to this question 6 (20%) participants considered it is very important, 12 (40%) considered it is fairly important and 12 (40%) considered it not much important. Nobody opted for 'not at all' and 'extremely' as shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1

<i>Importance of learning Culture of Target Language</i>						
	Extremely	Very	Fairly	Not much	Not at all	Total
Participants	----	6 (20%)	12 (40%)	12 (40%)	-----	30 (100%)

4.1. Selected Comments:

Language and culture coexist.

In communication practical language is needed

4.2. Results & Discussion

Participants of the study consider culture of native speakers of language important to a limited extent as only 20 percent believed it is very important while other 80 percent considered it fairly or not much important. Here it is clear that if English is taught as an international language then the effect of native culture is there but to a limited extent. It is also supported by qualitative comments of the participants. It is also dependent on the teaching assignment if teachers are teaching traditional undergraduate classes, their focus is more on native culture as compare to the teachers of functional English courses where focus is more on non-native communicative activities. So participants' focus is less on native speakers' culture.

2. In response to this question, 18 (60%) participants considered most of the material and 12 (40%) believed some of the material. Nobody opted for 'all' and 'none' as shown in table 4.2.

Table 4.2

How much of the materials you used to teach native culture?

	All	Some	Most	None	Not at all
Participants	----	12 (40%)	18 (60%)	-----	30 (100%)

4.3. Selected Comments

Because of using foreign published books and materials.
 Local materials lack quality.

4.4. Results & Discussion

The result showed that most of the participants use good deal of material from the native speakers' culture but this is due to the materials available in the standardized textbooks available for teaching and lack of quality materials in locally produced books. This is the main theme of the qualitative comments made by the participants. So, most of the material they are currently using has native speakers' culture in abundance. Whatever the participants can do to reduce this they are doing but major part is target language's culture.

- In response to this question, 5 (16.6%) participants stated it is very important, 15 (50%) considered it is fairly important and 10 (33.3%) believed it is not much important. Nobody opted for 'not at all' and 'extremely' as shown in table 4.3.

Table 4.3

Importance of awareness of Cultural Diversity

	Extremely	Very	Fairly	Not much	Not at all	Total
Participants	----	5(16.6%)	15 (50%)	10 (33.33%)	-----	30 (100%)

4.5. Selected Responses

Limited exposure is needed for every learner.
 It helps them understand diversity of cultures.

4.6. Results & Discussion

Participants were in favour of making learners aware of linguistic and cultural differences in the various contexts in which English is learned and used. But they were not in favour of over doing it. Exposure is needed to all learners to become more tolerant and to become good members of global community.

- In response to this question, 28 (93.3%) participants selected the sequence of 'a' then 'b' then 'c'. Only 2 (6.7 %) chose 'b' first and 'a' later as shown in table 4.4.

Table 4.4

Type of cultural content preferred.

	ABC	BAC	CAB	BCA	ACB	Total
Participants	28 (93.3)	2(6.7)	-----	-----	-----	30 (100%)

4.7. Selected Comments

Comparison of different cultures provide variety for discussion and expressions
 Local culture improves understanding and motivates learners

4.8. Results & Discussion

Almost all the participants favoured content that belongs to the learners and then the native speakers' culture and then culture of other non-native countries. Only 2 participants put the native speakers' culture first and then of the learners. This clearly suggested what English language teachers think. As the qualitative comments also suggested that discussion and activities on local

culture are more motivating and enhance learning. But importance of native speakers’ culture and culture of other countries cannot be neglected.

- In response to *What do you think about the cultural content of English books*, all 30(100%) preferred local and international situations that are recognizable.

4.9. Results & Discussion

All participants agreed that books should include materials and activities based on local and international situations that are recognizable to the students. They should focus interaction between NS with NNS and also NNS with NNS, because most of the interaction at present is between non-native speakers of different regions. Interaction of non-natives with native speakers is limited. The participants were not in favour of activities based on only native speakers’ life and culture.

- In response to this question, 4.28 (93.3%) participants selected the sequence of ‘a’ then ‘b’ then ‘c’. Only 2 (6.7 %) chose ‘b’ first and ‘a’ later. Shown in table 4.5.

Table 4.5

Cultural content liked by students.

	ABC	BAC	CAB	BCA	ACB	Total
Participants	28 (93.3)	2(6.7)	-----	-----	-----	30 (100%)

4.10. Selected Comments

Existing knowledge helps in learning new knowledge.

It increases motivation of the learners.

4.11. Results & Discussion

The participants stated that their learners also like to learn English language through their own culture and life more but they are also interested in native speakers’ life and culture and thirdly in the cultures around the world. Participants thought that their learners feel motivated when they can relate to the materials presented in English, when they can identify their places, people and culture. They were also ready to accept divergent cultures too.

- In response to this question all participants said ‘yes’ i.e. 30(100%), but there was distribution in 2nd part as 15 (50%) participants said ‘they will tell the students that they don’t know’, 10 (33.33%) participants ‘ignored the question’ and 5 (16.6%) ‘invented an answer’ as shown in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6

Problem with cultural knowledge and response to question

	A	b	C	others	Total
Participants	10(33.33%)	5 (16.7%)	15 (50%)	-----	30 (100%)

4.12. Results & Discussion

All of the participants had faced the situations where they were asked about the cultural information for which they had no answer. As non-native speakers of language the participants don’t have complete awareness of the native speakers’ culture. As far as responding to the question is concerned most of the participants buy time some through ignoring the question and others through admitting their lack of knowledge at the moment and searching for the answer later. Few quickly invent the answer to save their reputation. They might do the correction later if their initial

guess was wrong. This suggests that most of the teachers have positive attitude towards learning of newer elements of native speaker's life and culture.

8. In response to this questions, 22 (73.33%) participants selected 'very often' and 8 (26.7 %) chose 'rarely'. Nobody opted for never and always as shown in table 4.7.

Table 4.7

Awareness of linguistic and cultural diversity

	Always	Sometimes	Very often	Rarely	Never	Total
Participants	-----	-----	8(26.7%)	22(73.33%)	-----	30 (100%)

4.13. Selected Comments

We have limited knowledge of other cultures

Books do not support such discussion

4.14. Results & Discussion

Participants provided very limited opportunities to the learners to get familiar with diversity of cultures present in the world. The reason is not that they did not want to but the reason is the non-availability of authentic materials and lack of anything like this in the books that they are teaching. They were providing the exposure but of very limited nature. There should be some trainings regarding this issue.

9. In response to this question *who can be a better choice for teaching English*, all participants i.e. 30 (100%) opted for option of 'multilingual non-native teacher' and none opted for 'native teacher without understanding of local culture.

4.15. Results & Discussion

This can be a biased result as all the respondents were non-native teachers of English but the fact which is stated in previous questions also backed the choice made by the participants. They all thought that non-native multilingual teacher is best suited because this teacher is more aware of the problems and cultural orientations of the learners. Native speaker might not be able to do the job the participants think.

10. What focus do the following areas receive during your English lessons?

a. Life, politics, economy and society of British/American people. In response to this part of question 10, 21 (70%) participants considered that focus is 'sufficient' while 9 (30%) participants believed that focus is 'too much' as shown in table 4.8.

Table 4.8

Focus on native speakers' social life

	Too much	Sufficient	Need more	Not at all	Total
Participants	9 (30%)	21 (70%)	-----	-----	30 (100%)

b. Life, politics, economy and society of your own country. In response to this question, 9(30%) of participants opted for 'not at all'. 13 (43.33%) participants opted for 'need more' and 8 (26.66%) opted for 'sufficient' options as shown in table 4.9.

Table 4.9

Focus on Learners' social life

	Too much	Sufficient	Need more	Not at all	Total
Participants	-----	8 (26.66%)	13 (43.33%)	9 (30%)	30 (100%)

c. Comparing life, politics, economy and society of people in different countries. In response to this question, 24(80%) participants opted for 'not at all' option and 6(20%) opted for need more option as shown in table 4.10.

Table 4.10

Focus on social life of other non-native countries

	Too much	Sufficient	Need more	Not at all	Total
Participants	-----	-----	6 (20%)	24 (80%)	30 (100%)

4.16. Results & Discussion

This question was answered by the participants according to their current teaching assignments not how they want it to be. Current ELT books have either too much or sufficient native speakers' life and culture. The life and culture of learners is not sufficient and it needs more to be added. And the life and culture of other non-native countries is extremely limited. This also depends on the teaching assignments. The language teaching books that are locally produced have relatively more local content than internationally produced books. This suggests that participants were in favour of teaching local as well as international culture for the benefit of their students.

11. What percentage of cultural content you want in ELT materials? In response to this question, 16 (53.33%) participants opted for option 'e' and 14(46.66) participants opted for option 'd'. Other options were not considered by the participants as shown in table 4.11

4.17. Options

a. Native Culture 80%	Learner's Culture 10%	Non-Native Culture 10%
b. Native Culture 50%	Learner's Culture 25%	Non-Native Culture 25%
c. Native Culture 60%	Learner's Culture 30%	Non-Native Culture 10%
d. Native Culture 50%	Learner's Culture 35%	Non-Native Culture 15%
e. Native Culture 40%	Learner's Culture 40%	Non-Native Culture 20%

Table 4.11

Percentage of cultural content in ELT materials

	a	B	C	D	e	Total
Participants	-----	-----	-----	14(46.66%)	16(53.33%)	30 (100%)

4.18. Results & Discussion

This question authenticated the results of previous questions because here the attitude of the participants was very clear. They wanted that 40 to 50 percent of the cultural content should belong to native speakers' life and culture because it was important but 50 to 60 percent of the cultural content should belong to local and other non-native cultures. Furthermore 35 to 40 percent of the cultural material should focus local or learners' life and culture and 15 to 20 percent of the cultural material should focus other non-native cultures. This showed the understanding of participants regarding culture in ELT materials and they were clear about their choices.

5. Conclusion & Recommendations

The research showed that Pakistani teachers were well aware of the cultural elements in ELT materials. They were adapting and adopting the most recent trends like teaching of English as an International language. They were also aware of the effect of globalization that is why they emphasized on the use of all cultures to a varying degrees. They were aware of the identity of their learners that is why promoting the use of local culture in English language teaching to considerable extent. They were also aware that their learners were going to interact more with non-native

speakers of English as compared to native speakers of English that is why trying to include divergent cultures in their teaching and proposing the same for the ELT materials.

5.1. Recommendations for Book authors

Following are the recommendations for book authors can be given on the basis of the research:

- a. Local culture should be given 40 to 50 percent of space in the ELT materials to make English language more enjoyable and motivating to the students.
- b. Native speakers' life and culture is important but more global aspects of the culture should be focused.
- c. Native speakers' life and culture which is part of language can take 40 to 50 percent of space in ELT materials to make learning more authentic.
- d. Cultures of non-native speaking countries can take 10 to 20 percent space in ELT materials for creating world awareness, inculcating tolerance and promoting peace.
- e. Activities in ELT materials should include interactions between NNS as well as NS.
- f. Teachers should be properly trained for teaching of diversified cultures.

5.2. Recommendations for Future Research

1. Students should be investigated for their perceptions regarding cultural orientation in ELT materials.
2. Experimental study of teaching English through native speakers' cultural content against local cultural content can be undertaken.
3. Impact of global language on local culture can be studied.

References:

- Adaskou, K., Britten, D., & Fahsi, B. (1990). Design decisions on the cultural content of a secondary English course for Morocco (pp. 3–10): *ELT Journal*.
- Alptekin, C. (2002). Towards intercultural communicative competence (pp. 57–64): *ELT Journal*.
- Alptekin, C. Alptekin, M. (1984). The question of culture: EFL teaching in non-English speaking countries (pp. 14-20): *ELT journal*.
- Baker, W. (2011). Intercultural awareness: Modelling an understanding of cultures in intercultural communication through English as a lingua franca (pp.197–214): *Language and Intercultural Communication*.
- Baker, W. (2012). From cultural awareness to intercultural awareness: Culture in ELT (pp. 62–70): *ELT Journal*.
- Baker, W. (2015). Research into practice: Cultural and intercultural awareness (pp. 130–141): *Language Teaching*.

- Bolton, K. (2004). World Englishes. In A. Davies & C. Elder (Eds.), *The handbook of applied linguistics* (pp. 369–396). Oxford: Blackwell.
- Brown, H. D. (1994). *Teaching by Principles*: Prentice Hall.
- Brown, H.D. (1980). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice Hall.
- Brown, J. D. (2012). EIL curriculum development. In L. Alsagoff, G. Hu, & S. L. McKay, W. A. Renandya (Eds.), *Principles and practices for teaching English as an International language* (pp. 147–167). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Byram, M. (1988). *Cultural studies in foreign language education*. Clevedon, PA: Multilingual Matters.
- Byram, M. (1997). *Teaching and assessing interculturalcommunicative competence*. Clevedon, PA: Multilingual Matters.
- Byram, M., Gribkova, B., & Starkey, H. (2002). *Developing the intercultural dimension in language teaching: A practical introduction for teachers*. The Council of Europe.
- Campbell, D. et al. (1982). English in international settings: problems and their causes. In: L Smith. (ed.) (1983): *Readings in English as an international language*. London: Pergamon Press.
- Canagarajah, S. (2006). Changing communicative needs, revised assessment objectives: Testing English as an international language. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 3, 229–242.
- Chohan, M.N., (2016). A comparative study of Rural and Urban EFL Secondary school students towards usefulness and liking of English in Punjab, Pakistan. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 21 (9) (Sep. 2016), 22-28.
- Chohan, M. N., Abbas, F., & Saleem, M. (2018). CALL as a tool in teaching EFL in Pakistani religious institutes (Madaris): A survey of issues and challenges. *Al-Qalam*, 23(1), 65-74.
- Chohan, M. N., & Akhtar, M. T. Changing attitude for the English language in Pakistani Religious Seminaries.
- Chomsky, N. (1966). *Linguistic Theory*. Reprinted in J.P.B. Allen and P. Van Buren (eds.) *Chomsky: Selected Readings*, pp. 152-9. London: Oxford.
- Cogo, A., & Dewey, M. (2012). *Analysing English as a lingua franca: A corpus-driven investigation*. London: Continuum.
- Cunningsworth. A. (1995). *Choosing your Coursebook*: Macmillan Heineman. doi:10.1017/S0261444814000287
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1973). *Explorations in the Functions of Language*. London: Edward Arnold.
- Hornby, A.S. (1954). *A Guide to Patterns and Usage in English*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Hornby, A.S., E.V. Gatenbt, and H. Wakefield. (1953). *The Advanced Learner’s Dictionary of Current English*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Howatt, A. P. R. (1984). *A History of English Language Teaching*. Oxford. Oxford University Press.
- Hymes, D. (1972). On communicative competence. In J. B. Pride and J. Holmes (eds.), *Sociolinguistics*, pp. 269—93. Harmondsworth: Penguin.
- Jenkins, J. (2006). Current perspectives on teaching world Englishes and English as a lingua franca. *TESOL Quarterly*, 40, 157–181.
- Jenkins, J. (2009). English as a lingua franca: Interpretations and attitudes. *World Englishes*, 28, 200–207.

- Kachru, B. B. (1985). Standards, codification, and sociolinguistic realm: The English language in the outer circle. In R. Quirk & H. G. Widdowson (Eds.), *English in the world* (pp. 11–30). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kachru, B. B. (1986). *The alchemy of English: The spread functions and models of non-native Englishes*. Oxford: Pergamon.
- Kachru, B. B. (Ed.). (1992). *The other tongue: English across cultures* (2nd ed.). Urbana: University of Illinois Press.
- Kelly, L. G. (1969). 25 Centuries of Language Teaching. Rowley, Mass. Newbury House.
- Kumaravadivelu, B. (2012). Individual identity, cultural globalization, and teaching English as an international language. In L. Alsagoff, G. Hu, & S. L. McKay, W. A. Renandya (Eds.), *Principles and practices for teaching English as an International language* (pp. 9–27). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Lightbown, P. M. and Spada, N. (1993). *How languages are learned*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Matsuda, A. (2003). The ownership of English in Japanese secondary schools. *World Englishes*, 22, 483–496.
- Matsuda, A. (2012). Teaching material in EIL. In L. Alsagoff, G. Hu, & S. L. McKay, W. A. Renandya (Eds.), *Principles and practices for teaching English as an international language* (pp.168–185). New York, NY: Routledge.
- McDonough, J. & Shaw, C. (1993). *Materials and Methods in ELT*: Blackwell.
- McKay, S. (2010). English as an international language. In N. Hornberger & S. L. McKay (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics and language education* (pp. 89–115). Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- McKay, S. (2012). Principles of teaching English as an international language. In L. Alsagoff, G. Hu, & S. L. McKay, W. A. Renandya (Eds.), *Principles and practices for teaching English as an international language* (pp. 28–46). New York, NY: Routledge.
- McKay, S. L. (2002). *Teaching English as an international language*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- McKay, S. L., & BokhorstHeng, W. D. (2008). *International English in its sociolinguistic contexts: Towards a socially sensitive EIL pedagogy*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Nunan, D. (1999/ 2000). Yes, but is English? *TESOL Matters*, 3.
- Palmer, H.E., and F.G. Blandford. (1939). *A Grammar of Spoken English on a Strictly Phonetic Basis*. Cambridge. Heffer.
- Quirk, R. (1978). Aspects of English as an International language. *Spoglaereren* 9: 15-28.
- Sharifian, F. (2009). *English as an international language: Perspectives and pedagogical issues*. Bristol, MA: Multilingual Matters.
- Shaw, D. (1981). "Asian students attitudes towards English." In: Smith, L. (ed.) (1983): *Readings in English as an international language*. London, Pergamon Press: 21-29.
- Sheldon, L. (1988). Evaluating ELT textbooks and materials. *ELT Journal* Vol. 37/3: Oxford University Press.
- Skierso, A. (1991). Textbook selection and adaptation. In Celce-Murcia, M. (ed.) *Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language*: Newbury House.
- Skinner, B. F. (1957). *Verbal Behavior*. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts.
- Smith, L. E. (1978). Some distinctive features of EIL vs. ESOL in English language education. In: Smith, L. (ed.) (1981): *English for cross-cultural communication* (pp. 13-21). London: Macmillan.

- Smith. L. E. (1981). English as international language. In: Id. (ed.) (1983): *Readings in English as an international language*. London, Pergamon Press: 1-8.
- Smith. L. E. (ed.) (1981). English for cross-cultural communication. London: Macmillan.
- Smith. L.E. (1976). English as international auxiliary language. *RELC Journal*, 7: 1-8.
- Spitzberg, B. H., & Chagnon, G. (2009). Conceptualizing intercultural communication competence. In D. K. Deardorff (Ed.), *The SAGE handbook of intercultural competence* (pp. 2–52). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Stern. H. H. (1992). *Issues and options in language teaching*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Talebinezhad, M. R./Aliakbari, M. (2001). Basic assumptions in Teaching English as an International Language. The Internet TESL

Appendix. A

Questionnaire: Culturally oriented ELT Textbooks and English Language Teachers

Dear Colleagues:

I greatly appreciate you completing the following short questionnaire which seeks to investigate your opinion regarding culture and varieties of English. Your information will remain confidential and data will be used only for research purposes. Research topic: Culturally oriented ELT Textbooks and English Language Teachers.

Name: (Optional)

Age: (Choose) 51 41–50 31–40 : 21–30

Gender: Female Male

Years of teaching experience:

10+ 5–10 1–5 0–1

Professional qualifications:

BA in English Language and Literature

Other _____ MA in _____

Nationality:

Questions:

1. Do you think it is important to learn about the culture of speakers of a language when we learn that language?

not at all not much fairly very extremely

Briefly give reasons for your answer:

2. How much of the materials you use teaches the culture of native speaker countries (i.e. the USA or UK)?

none some most all

Briefly give reasons for your answer:

3. How much do you think English materials should provide students with awareness of linguistic and cultural differences in the various contexts in which English is learned and used?

not at all not much fairly very extremely

Briefly give reasons for your answer:

4. Which type of cultural content would you prefer to use in your English class? (Number them according to your preference)

A—Cultural content that deals with local places and people of your country.

B—Cultural content that deals primarily with aspects of United States or British life and culture.

C—Cultural content that deals with the life and culture of various countries around the world.

5. What do you think about the cultural content of English books? (Choose One)
- (a) It should include materials and activities based on local and international situations that are recognizable and applicable to the students' everyday lives, pertaining to both NS–NNS and NNS–NNS interactions.
 - (b) It should include activities and materials that deal primarily with aspects of United States or British life and culture.
6. Which type of cultural content do you feel that your students like best? (Number them according to your preference)
- A—Content that deals with local places and people of their own country.
 - B—Content that deals primarily with aspects of United States or British life and culture.
 - C—Content that deals with the life and culture of various countries around the world.

Briefly give reasons for your answer:

7. Have you ever been asked questions about cultural information in a textbook that you could not answer?
- A—Yes.
 - B—No.
- If **yes**, what did you do?
- A—I ignored the question.
 - B—I quickly invented an answer.
 - C—I told the students that I didn't know but that I would try to find out.
 - D—Other: _____

8. Do you try to provide students with awareness of linguistic and cultural differences in the various contexts in which English is learned and used other than providing them with just Native British or American English?
- always sometimes very often rarely never

Briefly give reasons for your answer:

9. Who can be a better choice in teaching English in a local community?
- (a) Multilingual non-native teacher because of being familiar with local culture can better attend to the needs of learners.
 - (b) Native English teacher can be a better choice and culture has no role in this matter.
10. What focus do the following areas receive during your English lessons?
- a. Life, politics, economy and society of British/American people**
 not at all need more sufficient too much
 - b. Life, politics, economy and society of your own country**
 not at all need more sufficient too much
 - c. Comparing life, politics, economy and society of people in different countries**
 not at all need more sufficient too much

11. What percentage of cultural content you want in ELT materials

- | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|------------------------|
| a. Native Culture 80% | Learner's Culture 10% | Non-Native Culture 10% |
| b. Native Culture 50% | Learner's Culture 25% | Non-Native Culture 25% |
| c. Native Culture 60% | Learner's Culture 30% | Non-Native Culture 10% |
| d. Native Culture 50% | Learner's Culture 35% | Non-Native Culture 15% |
| e. Native Culture 40% | Learner's Culture 40% | Non-Native Culture 20% |